

US Economic Outlook after Covid-19 Outbreak

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Abstract

The 2019 corona virus outbreak that has advanced into 2022 has profoundly affected the United States Citizenry. Many businesses, households, and governments took takes to impose restrictions such as social distancing, closed businesses and schools, working from home and limiting of social gatherings to slow the spread of the virus. The measures taken to impede the spread of the virus caused the closing of business or curtailing of business operations and government activities. Manufacturing was affected, a factor that resulted into the disruption of global and local supply chains and caused a decrease in good demanded. The disruptions to economic activity slowed down expansion and precipitated acute labor market conditions deterioration. Policy makers are taking steps to support the economic rebound in response to the previous slowdown. This paper aims to give an economic outlook of the United States economy for the year 2020-2021.

The US economic outlook

The economy of the United States is one of the most affected countries by the Corona virus outbreak. The economy of the United States began to recover in the second half of the year 2020 as pandemic concerns started diminishing and the state and local government restriction began to ease. The labor market is expected to improve materially after the third quarter with hiring expected to rebound and furloughs projected to significantly fall as social; distancing degree decreases (Michelsen, 2020). The pandemic restrictions and social distancing are expected to continue but on a declining trend to account or the reemergence and persistence chances of the outbreak. The social distancing persistence will continue to suppress the economic activity as well as the labor market conditions for some time. All the variables factored into the

real GDP, consumer spending, exports, imports and government spending and private sector spending are expected to rise in the coming future.

The real consumer spending (Inflation-adjusted) accounts for more than half of the gross domestic product. The reduced demand of goods and services and limited business operations. The corona virus spread containment measures by both federal and local governments greatly curtailed consumer spending cutting it down by 28%. Spending on goods such as clothing and services such as accommodation dropped by similar margin. The spending rose in the initial stages of the pandemic when people were stockpiling items in anticipation for the social distancing measures by the authorities (Michelsen, 2020).

The economic activity decline happened so rapidly that the depth of the economic downturn is still uncertain. The reduction in consumer spending was the reason behind the contraction of the real GDP. This drop was also contributed to by the decline in investment as oil and gas drills, construction employment, architectural billing index, car and light trucks sale and mortgage applications fell.

A decline was also registered in flows of exports and imports since the onset of the pandemic with trade in travel services including air travels and accommodation. These came as a result of international travel restrictions that also affected exports and imports of travel services. Good export and import also contracted with motor vehicle and parts among others showed weaknesses. These contractions in exports and imports resulted in the closure and slow down of some businesses. These contractions came as a result of the health concerns which in turn led to a fall in demand of goods and services in the country and in other countries that are the largest trading partners such as China, Canada, Mexico and Japan and other euro zone countries.

The United States, being at the centre of the crisis, its economy was affected directly by the mortgage market meltdown, financial crisis and credit crunch. As a result, the economy shrunk with reduction in Gross Domestic Product, inflation, increased public debt and increased taxation. The same scenarios were continued to show signs of persistence through the better part of the year with the increased riots witnessed in the country. The financial crisis and the subsequent recession brought the need for new economic thinking (Clarida, 2020). This included the exclusion of financial system (capital markets and credit relationships, both lenders and borrowers and sellers and buyers of securities) from the Dynamic Stochastic General Equilibrium and reinstatement of distribution, backing off from intellectual imperialism and learning from history.

The subsequent legislations in the country such as stimulus packages and tax credits to individuals are expected to boost the demand of goods and services. The payments and the tax credits will provide resources in the face of lost income by households. The federal assistance to state and local governments is also expected to pay for rising expenditures attributed to tax falls at both state and local levels. Grants and loan are also expected to provide liquidity to ailing businesses, increase their survival likelihood and preserve jobs until economic activity picks up. The payments made to health providers are also expected to provide further support to the treatment and containment of the virus and increase spending.

The economic activity boost by recent legislations will greatly help in the nation's economic recovery. However, if the virus containment measures such as social distancing, lockdowns, business closures and reduced working hours continue, the supply and demand of many goods and services will continue to be curtailed. It is, therefore, estimated that economic boost efforts will revive the economy of the United States as long as the virus containment measures

are lifted as has been witnessed in the recent past. However, the continuation of the virus containment measures will tamper with the expected growth. In this case, spending by businesses and individuals will further be hampered by the social distancing and the partial lockdown measures. These will be recovered once the stay-at-home orders and other measures will be lifted (Burton et al, 2020).

The economic activity is projected to fell by the second quarter but is expected to start showing rising signs in the third quarter. The real GDP is therefore expected to start rising in the second half of the year as labor market conditions will start improving in the third quarter. The legislations will moderate economic activity rebound as customer spending will be boosted. Despite the expected improvement of economic activity in the third quarter, the real GDP and employment is expected to lower than their 2019 levels due to the gradual recovery pattern.

References

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